

4-Quinazolones. Part X

Synthesis of Some Thiazolo (3, 2-a) quinazolonium Salts

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The synthesis of some 1-aryl-4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-4-phenylthiazolo(3,2-a)quinazolin-10-ium salts is described.

In recent years several heteroaromatic systems having a fused thiazolium ring have been synthesised¹. In general, their preparation involved the transformation of the heterocyclic compounds containing a thioamide group as a part of their cycle into the corresponding ketosulfides by interaction with ω -halo ketones or ω -halo aldehyde acetals and subsequent cyclisation to fused thiazolium heterocyclic systems as shown below :—

Our interest^{2a,b} in the *N*-bridgehead compounds derived from 3-phenyl-2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one prompted us to apply this reaction for the formation of thiazolo(3,2-a)quinazolonium system (II) which has not been so far reported in the literature. As starting compounds we employed 2-phenacylthio-, 2-*p*-bromophenacylthio-, and 2-*p*-hydroxyphenacylthio-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (Ia,b,c) which were prepared earlier^{2a} by us. These ketosulfides were cyclised in the presence of conc. sulphuric acid into 1,4-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo(3,2-a)-quinazolin-10-ium (IIa), 1-*p*-bromophenyl- and 1-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-4-phenylthiazolo(3,2-a)quinazolin-10-ium (II) sulphates respectively. Alternatively, the cyclisation was also effected with polyphosphoric acid (PPA) and the products were isolated as their perchlorate salts. The acid-catalysed cyclodehydration in these instances may be accounted for by the mechanism put forward by Bradsher and Lohr Jr.³ for such type of cyclisation.

1. B. Stanovnik, M. Tisler and A. Vrbanic, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, :996 and references cited therein.
- 2a. B. D. Singh and (Late) D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 759.
- b. B. D. Singh and (Late) D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 759.
3. C. K. Bradsher and D. F. Lohr, Jr., *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1966, **3**, 27.

Our attempts to cyclise 3-benzenesulphonyl-2-phenacyl/*p*-bromophenacylthioquinazolin-4(3H)-ones^{2b}, however, proved unsuccessful and in both cases the unchanged starting materials were recovered. The failure may be attributed to the insolubility of these keto sulfides in concentrated sulphuric acid and in polyphosphoric acid (PPA).

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Aryl-4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-4-phenylthiazolo(3,2-*a*)quinazolin-10-ium (II) salts : Following the published procedure¹ these were prepared as follows :

(a) *Cyclisation with Conc. H₂SO₄* : The keto sulfide (I; 0.5 g.) was treated with conc. H₂SO₄ (5 ml.) and the mixture allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hr. The yellowish solution was carefully poured into ice-cold ether (100 ml.). After some time an oil separated. The ether layer was removed, the residual oil diluted with water (10 ml.) and the aq. solution, on standing for about 5 min. in ice-water, deposited colourless crystalline precipitate. After further dilution with cold water, the solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised to afford II as sulphate.

IIa Sulphate : needles from methanol. Yield, 0.4 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 58.34; H, 3.66; N, 6.00. C₂₂H₁₆N₂S₂O₅ requires : C, 58.47; H, 3.53; N, 6.19%.

IIb Sulphate : prisms from methanol, yield, 0.42 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 49.47; H, 2.74; N, 5.20. C₂₂H₁₅N₂S₂O₅Br requires : C, 49.71; H, 2.82; N, 5.27%.

IIb Sulphate : needles; no suitable solvent for crystallisation could be found. It was purified by repeated washing with hot methanol. Yield 0.4 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 56.20; H, 3.24; N, 5.85. C₂₂H₁₆N₂S₂O₆ requires : C, 56.41; H, 3.41; N, 5.95%.

(b) *Cyclisation with PPA* : The keto sulfide (I; 0.5 g.) was mixed with commercial PPA (12 g.) and heated in an oil bath kept at 150° for 2 hr. The clear solution was poured into ice-water, the solution filtered and the filtrate treated with a few drops of 70% HClO₄. The colourless crystalline precipitate that separated out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised to afford II as perchlorate.

IIa Perchlorate : rectangular plates from glacial acetic acid, yield 0.41 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 58.33; H, 3.47; N, 6.40. C₂₂H₁₅N₂SClO₅ requires : C, 58.08; H, 3.30; N, 6.16%.

IIb Perchlorate : plates from glacial acetic acid, yield 0.4 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 49.54; H, 2.76; N, 5.18. C₂₂H₁₄N₂O₅SClBr requires : C, 49.48; H, 2.62; N, 5.24%.

IIc Perchlorate : needles; no suitable solvent for crystallisation could be found. It was purified by repeated washing with hot methanol. Yield 0.38 g.; m.p. > 300°. Found : C, 56.30; H, 3.35; N, 6.10. C₂₂H₁₅N₂SO₆Cl requires : C, 56.11; H, 3.19; N, 5.95%.